

OPTIMIZATION OF TOOTH MOVEMENT IN THE POST-EXTRACTION SPACE DURING ORTHODONTIC TREATMENT OF OCCLUSION ANOMALIES

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ABSTRACT

Optimization of tooth movement in the post-extraction space in orthodontic treatment of occlusion anomalies is aimed at improving results and reducing treatment time through the use of modern technologies and methods. Problems associated with post-extraction tooth movement include instability of tooth position, disruption of interdental contacts and the possibility of relapse. This paper examines the main aspects of the biomechanics of tooth movement after extraction, as well as optimization methods, such as the use of mini-implants, orthodontic anchor systems and individual orthodontic appliances. Particular attention is paid to reducing the risk of unwanted movements and improving the long-term stability of results. Treatment optimization allows minimizing complications associated with the aesthetics and function of the dentition, improving the quality of life of patients and increasing the effectiveness of orthodontic intervention.

Introduction

Orthodontic treatment of occlusion anomalies, especially in cases where tooth extraction is required, is a complex and multi-stage task. Tooth movement in the post-extraction space requires careful diagnostics, detailed planning and the use of individualized methods that allow the effective use of the released space to achieve optimal functional and aesthetic results. The creation of a suitable occlusal contact, the correct position of the teeth in the row and symmetrical relationship of the jaws is ensured by the use of the post-extraction space, which becomes a key element in the correction of occlusal anomalies.

Goals and objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to analyze and substantiate modern approaches to optimizing tooth movement in the post-extraction space, as well as to develop recommendations for improving the effectiveness of treatment. The main objectives include:

- 1. Study of the biological basis of tooth movement:** consideration of bone and soft tissue remodeling processes under mechanical load, as well as factors that contribute

to the reduction of treatment time and improvement of the stability of the achieved result.

2. **Analysis of factors influencing the efficiency of post-extraction space use:** study of key variables such as patient age, type of anomaly, bone tissue condition and treatment methods used.
3. **Review of modern orthodontic technologies and devices:** determination of the advantages of various systems and methods aimed at optimal use of post-extraction space and minimization of possible complications.

Biological aspects of tooth movement

Tooth movement in orthodontics is based on complex biological processes of tissue adaptation to the effect of directed mechanical forces. Under the influence of orthodontic pressure, bone tissue remodeling, stretching and compression of the periodontal ligament occur. Optimization of tooth movement should take into account:

- **Biological activity of tissues:** the ability of bone tissue and periodontal ligament to adapt is an important aspect for rapid and stable tooth movement.
- **Risk of root resorption:** Excessive pressure can cause irreversible damage to the roots of teeth, so force dosage and control of tissue adaptation are important.
- **Bone remodeling:** For successful relocation, it is necessary to control the processes of resorption and formation of new bone tissue to avoid undesirable consequences such as bone loss or tooth instability.

Factors Affecting Optimization of Tooth Movement

1. **Type of malocclusion.** The choice of appropriate treatment method depends on the nature of the malocclusion. For example, in the case of a deep bite, methods aimed at changing the vertical relationship of the jaws can be used, while in the case of crowded teeth, the main focus is on widening the dental arch and using the post-extraction space to align the teeth.
2. **Age of the patient.** In patients under 20, the processes of bone tissue regeneration and adaptation occur more quickly, which contributes to more effective tooth movement. Adult patients, especially those with signs of osteoporosis, require a more cautious approach given the slow bone turnover and increased risk of complications.
3. **Mechanotherapy methods.** The use of innovative technologies, such as self-adjusting braces and transparent aligners, contributes to an even distribution of force and reduced friction, which allows for more effective use of the post-extraction space and improves control over tooth movement.
4. **Bone remodeling and tissue support.** It is important to consider the condition and density of bone tissue when choosing a technique for moving teeth. If necessary, additional methods such as microosteoperforation or osteoplasty are used to improve tissue regeneration and stability.

Modern methods for moving teeth in the post-extraction space

- **Mini-implants and mini-plates.** These devices are used as auxiliary supports for applying targeted forces, which improves the predictability of tooth movement. They allow you to create stable support points that minimize unwanted movement of adjacent teeth and speed up the correction process.
- **Self-ligating bracket systems.** By reducing friction, self-ligating systems allow for more comfortable tooth movement and better control over movement in the post-extraction space. They also reduce treatment time and reduce patient discomfort.

- *Aligners (transparent caps).* Aligners provide the ability to gradually and controlled tooth movement, which minimizes the risk of impact on adjacent teeth and improves the accuracy of using the post-extraction space. They are especially convenient for adult patients who prefer less noticeable orthodontic solutions.
- *Integration of digital technologies.* Modern orthodontic programs allow you to create digital models of the dentition and predict tooth movement with high accuracy. The use of 3D technologies and modeling makes it possible to plan treatment more accurately, which is especially important in case of complex occlusion anomalies and limited post-extraction space.

Practical application and recommendations

Optimization of tooth movement in the post-extraction space requires an integrated approach that takes into account all the individual characteristics of the patient. Recommended:

Comprehensive diagnostics: the use of CBCT, orthopantomography and 3D modeling to accurately determine the volume and condition of bone tissue, planning the direction and force of tooth movement.

Regular treatment monitoring: monitoring the condition of bone and soft tissue at each stage of treatment to prevent possible complications.

Individual approach to the choice of treatment methods: preference for methods that correspond to the age and biological characteristics of the patient. If necessary, it is recommended to combine methods to achieve a more predictable result.

Conclusion

Optimization of tooth movement in the post-extraction space is an important aspect of modern orthodontic treatment of occlusion anomalies. The use of the latest technologies, such as mini-implants, self-ligating brackets, transparent caps and digital modeling, combined with an understanding of the biological processes of tissue adaptation, allows to reduce treatment time, reduce the risk of complications and improve both functional and aesthetic indicators.

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